

Poster: Impact of Temporary Location Visitors on Mobile App Usage in French Cities: Implications for Socio-Economic Segregation Studies

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Abstract. This study investigates the determinants of mobile app usage patterns in a 4G network across 20 French cities, focusing on the relative influence of socioeconomic characteristics of temporary visitors and locals. Using the NetMob23 dataset and a range of spatial and socioeconomic data sources, we apply random forest models to predict mobile traffic. Our results indicate that accessibility-based variables, which reflect potential visitors, provide a better explanation of 4G data usage patterns compared to demographic characteristics of residents and the composition of land use. This suggests that mobile data traffic reflects temporary visitor behaviour rather than the socioeconomic profile of residents, challenging conventional interpretations of 4G usage data in studies on urban socioeconomic segregation and inequalities.

Submission Type. Analysis.

BoK Concepts. [AM11] Network analysis; [AM7] Spatial statistics; [GC3] Artificial intelligence (AI) in EO and GI.

Keywords. mobile app usage, accessibility, human mobility, segregation

1 Introduction

This study quantifies the factors associated with app usage patterns in a 4G network. In particular, we assess whether these patterns are influenced more by the potential presence of temporary visitors (non-residents) than by the socioeconomic characteristics of the location's residents. By addressing this question, we improve our understanding of the latent quantities that 4G network app usage measures,

with implications for what and how these types of data can be leveraged to estimate underlying quantities of interest (such as socio-economic inequalities and segregation).

Most recent research on the usage of apps and services on smartphones links this usage directly to the territory and associated land use composition (Furno et al., 2017; Miao et al., 2018; Xing et al., 2018; Novović et al., 2020) and to the socioeconomic profile of residents (Ucar et al., 2021; Goel et al., 2023). Most researchers (with few exceptions (Yu et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2019)), therefore, ignore the use of Wi-Fi (at home, work, or elsewhere). However, 4G traffic at a location can be influenced primarily by non-residents if local residents predominantly use Wi-Fi at home. (Singh et al., 2019) argue that the differences in the usage of mobile services cannot be explained by the differences in the coverage of Wi-Fi and cellular networks. Furthermore, the choice between Wi-Fi and cellular networks is not random and depends on whether the location is a known regular location (Oliveira et al., 2016). Studies across several countries have shown that users spend more time and use more data on Wi-Fi than on cellular connections (de Reuver and Bouwman, 2014; Hyun et al., 2016; Walelgne et al., 2021).

The NetMob23 (Martínez-Durive et al., 2023) data on the use of mobile apps and services in 20 French cities is tied to specific locations rather than information on individual smartphone users. Usage is captured exclusively via a 4G network, leaving out Wi-Fi and, therefore, likely representing more the behavior of temporary visitors. Thus, characterizing mobile data traffic in an area by the socioeconomic profile of residents of the area is likely to be misleading, and land use (pull factors) and accessibility (opportunity factors) have greater explanatory potential than

the socioeconomic characteristics of the residents (Ucar et al., 2021).

2 Materials & Methods

We use NetMob23 dataset (Martínez-Durive et al., 2023), which captures 4G network in traffic every 15 minutes across a 100×100 meter spatial grid by mobile app and service types for more than 70 days in spring of 2019. We use the following additional datasets to characterize NetMob23 dataset locations: (1) land use – Copernicus CORINE Land Cover (100 m resolution) and Imperviousness Density (10 m resolution) (European Union et al., 2018), as well as highly detailed (10 m resolution) Theia OSO Land Cover Map for France (Inglada et al., 2019); (2) socioeconomic profile – spatial polygons for French IRIS (National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information (IGN), 2016) and associated socioeconomic variables on income and age distribution (The National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies, 2019); (3) accessibility (travel time matrix between grid cells) – OpenStreetMap road network (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2015), data on public transit timetable and connectivity (STIF, 2023) and the **r5r R** package (Pereira et al., 2021).

For each grid cell in every city in the NetMob23 dataset, we characterize each location based on its physical infrastructure and resident population by determining the shares of specific land use types, the population counts by age and by mean income per resident individual. To define the potential of each location to attract people from other locations for work, leisure, and other activities, we calculated accessibility (Geurs et al., 2016): how many individuals by age group and income bracket can reach this particular location using public transit within the 60-minute interval. This accessibility measure is a proxy for the probability of individuals from different socioeconomic groups visiting a particular location conditional on travel time. The 60-minute interval for the Greater Paris area is identified empirically as the one that provides reasonable variability for different locations; for all other cities, the optimal cutoff was identified at 30 minutes.

We use random forest models to predict total traffic for each mobile app/service for several time intervals, matching the arrival time of potential visitors with the time when traffic is generated at each location. Two-thirds of the data is used for training, and one-third is used for testing/validation.

3 Results

Our results indicate that variables related to accessibility outweigh the socioeconomic characteristics of location and the composition of land use (see Fig. 1). This suggests that the potential for visits by individuals with certain income brackets or within specific age groups are more in-

fluential factors in determining mobile data usage patterns than the socioeconomic characteristics of residents and the composition of land use in a location. An out-of-sample validation (see Fig. 2) certifies that the results are reliable: for most services, out-of-sample predictions have high R-squared and reasonable (for the size of the grid cell) symmetric mean absolute percentage error.

Our findings show that accessibility variables that define potential visitors consistently have a greater impact on mobile usage than demographics of residents. This demonstrates that (1) accessibility is a strong proxy for mobility patterns, (2) temporary visitors shape mobile app usage more than residents, and (3) previous studies misattribute usage trends to residents, overlooking visitors' influence. Ignoring potential visitors can lead to misleading conclusions about segregation and inequalities.

Figure 1. Feature importance in random forest models predicting mobile traffic. The plot illustrates that socioeconomic characteristics of non-residents (potential visitors) hold significantly greater predictive importance than those of residents. Consequently, excluding visitor-related variables would markedly reduce the model's explanatory power. Results presented here aggregate standardized feature importance values from separate models trained individually for each mobile app or service. Due to substantial variation in absolute traffic volumes across different services, feature importance values have been standardized to facilitate comparability. The error bars indicate the range of standardized feature importance across all models.

Figure 2. Validation via out-of-sample model performance estimation. The training set (orange) comprises a random sample containing two-thirds of the data, while the testing (validation) set (blue) contains the remaining one-third. The plot demonstrates that out-of-sample predictions exhibit only marginally lower performance (in terms of R^2 and model error) compared to in-sample predictions, indicating that the model is not overfitting.

4 Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in preparing this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were utilized for language editing and improving grammar and sentence structure but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

Code and data availability. The analysis was done using **R**, with **targets** as a build system and **mlr3** as a modelling framework. The complete analysis code will be shared when the research presented in this poster proposal is published in a journal. Due to the data license restrictions, the raw data cannot be shared. Efforts will be made to provide synthetic data or preaggregated data that allow one to check the reproducibility of the code.

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